

Additional file 3: Explanatory statements mentioned when motives before biopsy were noted as “other”

Other explanatory statements for motives before biopsy

My son-in-law motivated me / My son-in-law participates in the study

I have rheumatoid arthritis myself

To solve my own symptoms

Because I was asked

I hope RA can be cured in the future and I will not be hindered anymore by this disease

For study purposes

Because participating in research is important
